

EVALUATION OF THE DISTRIBUTION AND METABOLISM OF
POLYPHENOLS DERIVED FROM CUPUASSU (*THEOBROMA GRANDIFLORUM*)
IN MICE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT BY UPLC-ESI-QTOF

**HELENA RUDGE DE MORAES BARROS^{1a*}, ROCÍO GARCÍA-VILLALBA^{2a},
FRANCISCO A. TOMÁS-BARBERÁN², MARIA INÉS GENOVESE¹**

¹ Departamento de Alimentos e Nutrição Experimental, Faculdade de Ciências Farmacêuticas, Universidade de São Paulo, Av. Prof. Lineu Prestes 580, Bloco 14, 05508-900, São Paulo, SP, Brazil. E-mail address: genovese@usp.br (M.I. Genovese)

² Research Group on Quality, Safety and Bioactivity of Plant Foods, CEBAS-CSIC, P.O. Box 164, 30100, Campus de Espinardo, Murcia, Spain. E-mail address: rgvillalba@cebas.csic.es (R. García-Villalba; fatomas@cebas.csic.es (F.A. Tomás-Barberán)

***Correspondence:** (Tel: 55-11-30911525; Fax: 55-11-38154410; e-mail:
lebarros79@hotmail.com)

^a These authors contributed equally to this work

"This manuscript has been accepted for publication in *Journal of Functional Foods* (2016), Volume 282, Pages 477–489. The final version is available online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2016.02.009>."

ABSTRACT

The fate and metabolism of epicatechin-derived proanthocyanidins and glucuronide and sulphate conjugates of the unusual 8-hydroxyflavones hypolaetin, isoscutellarein and hypolaetin methyl ether from cupuassu in the gastrointestinal tract of mice were evaluated. Fasted mice C57BL/6 (n=27) were administered a cupuassu phenolic extract by gavage. Tissue samples (stomach, small intestine, cecum, and colon) and faeces were collected at different times after dosing and then were analysed by UPLC-ESI-QTOF. Parent compounds were found mainly in the stomach and small intestine and lesser amounts were present in cecum and colon because of their transformation to microbial metabolites. Aglycones from flavone conjugates and diarylpropan-2-ol and phenyl valerolactone metabolites from epicatechin were detected in the cecum, colon and faeces. No further metabolism to smaller phenolic acids was observed. This metabolic profile could result from the gut microbiota modulation by this unique mixture of cupuassu flavonoids including proanthocyanidins and 8-hydroxyflavones. Parent compounds and metabolites could exert local effects in the gastrointestinal tract contributing to the host health.

Keywords: cupuassu; flavone glucuronide; procyanidins; microbial metabolism; gastrointestinal tract; UPLC-ESI-QTOF.

Chemical compounds studied in this article

(-) Epicatechin (PubChem CID: 72276), Procyanidin B2 (PubChem CID: 122738), Isoscutellarein-8-O- β -D-glucuronine (PubChem CID: 44258568), Hypolaetin-8-O- β -D-glucuronide 3''-sulfate (PubChem CID: 11272944).

32

33 **1. Introduction**

34 Cupuassu (*Theobroma grandiflorum* Willd. ex Spreng. K.) Schum. is a tropical
35 fruit widely cultivated in the North of Brazil, with the largest production in Pará,
36 followed by Amazonas, Rondônia and Acre. It is also grown in other South American
37 countries, including Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador and Venezuela (Lim, 2012).
38 Cupuassu, as cocoa, belongs to the *Theobroma* genus, and it is considered one of the
39 most popular fruits on the Amazonian market and it is the second within this genus in
40 terms of economic importance. The fruit pulp is highly appreciated because of its
41 characteristic acidic taste and intense fragrance and is widely used to prepare juices, ice
42 creams, sorbets, sweets, jellies and other desserts (Vriesmann, Silveira, & Petkowicz,
43 2010). The seeds have received special attention because of their potential for being
44 used in a similar way to that of cocoa seeds in chocolate or other derived products
45 (Cucaita, Hernández, & Gutiérrez, 2014).

46 Phytochemical studies have demonstrated that cupuassu pulp and seeds contain
47 potent antioxidant polyphenols including flavones, flavan-3-ols and proanthocyanidins
48 (**Figure 1**) (Pugliese, Tomás-Barberán, Truchado, & Genovese, 2013; Yang et al.,
49 2003). The 8-O- β -D-glucuronides and the corresponding 3''-sulphates of isoscutellarein
50 (5,7,8,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone), hypolaetin (5,7,8,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone) and
51 hypolaetin 3-methyl ether (5,7,8,4'-tetrahydroxy-3'-methoxy-flavone) were detected in
52 cupuassu seeds, and also in pulp at much lower concentrations (Pugliese et al., 2013).
53 Cupuassu also contains proanthocyanidins mainly derived from epicatechin, similar to
54 those found in other *Theobroma* species, in particular, *Theobroma cacao* (Pugliese et
55 al., 2013). As cocoa powder and extracts have a relevant application in functional foods
56 with different health-associated affects (mental, cardiovascular, metabolic, etc.) (Smith,
57 2013; Rabadan-Chávez et al., 2016), the study of cuspuassu is of interest due to its
58 phytochemical composition that combines cocoa-like flavan-3-ols and
59 proanthocyanidins with anti-inflammatory 8-hydroxyflavones (Tomás-Barberán,
60 Mañez, & Villar, 1987).

61 Health beneficial properties have been proposed for cupuassu, being the
62 antioxidant capacity one of the most studied (Pinent et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2010).
63 The antidiabetic potential was also evaluated and cupuassu fruit showed the most potent
64 inhibition of α -amylase activity among sixteen Brazilian native fruits and six

65 commercial frozen pulps (Gonçalves, Lajolo, & Genovese, 2010). The effect of daily
66 intake of cupuassu liquor, prepared from fermented seeds, on oxidative stress and lipid
67 profile of rats with streptozotocin-induced diabetes was recently evaluated, showing that
68 supplementation with cupuassu liquor resulted in reduced plasma triacylglycerol levels,
69 increased HDL cholesterol levels and improved plasma antioxidant capacity (Oliveira &
70 Genovese, 2013). Chronic intake of a phenolic-rich extract from cupuassu liquor upon
71 metabolic changes associated with a high fat diet decreased lipid peroxidation,
72 increased plasma antioxidant capacity and improved glucose tolerance (Oliveira,
73 Rogero, & Genovese, 2015).

74 All these beneficial effects have been attributed to the presence of phenolic
75 compounds. However, to promote the biological effects a chemical compound must be
76 bioavailable to reach the systemic circulation and the target tissues (Rein et al., 2013).
77 Flavonoids have shown low bioavailability with levels of plasma and tissue metabolites
78 rarely exceeding nanomolar concentrations (Chen, Zheng, Li, & Jiang, 2014; Gonzales
79 et al., 2015). Higher concentrations of parent compounds and their primary metabolites
80 have been reported throughout the gastrointestinal tract, where they can exert their
81 beneficial effects and establish close contact with the intestinal microbiota (Cardona,
82 Andrés-Lacueva, Tulipani, Tinahones, & Queipo-Ortuño, 2013).

83 Although, extensive metabolism of different classes of flavonoids by the
84 microflora have been reported (Celep, Rastmanesh, & Marotta, 2014; Marín, Miguélez,
85 Villar, & Lombó, 2015; Selma, Espín, & Tomás-Barberán, 2009) little is known about
86 flavones and particularly about those present in cupuassu phenolic extract (CPE)
87 (hypolaetin and isoscutellarein) (Stanoeva & Stefova, 2013; Du et al., 2015). Regarding
88 procyanidins, it is known that the metabolites observed finally in the colon will depend
89 on the matrix being consumed. Therefore, although the microbial metabolism of
90 procyanidins has been extensively studied (Appeldoorn, Vincken, Aura, Hollman, &
91 Gruppen, 2009; Monagas et al., 2010; Urpi-Sarda et al., 2009), their distribution and
92 metabolic conversion in a unique matrix such as cupuassu, in combination with a very
93 different type of flavonoids (8-hydroxyflavones) deserves to be considered.

94 In this context, this study aimed to evaluate the gastrointestinal distribution and
95 metabolic conversion of polyphenols derived from CPE in an *in vivo* assay, using
96 C57BL/6 mice. Gastrointestinal bioavailability of cupuassu phenolic compounds may
97 help understanding the role of specific phenolic compounds in health effects. UPLC-

98 ESI-QTOF MS methodology was used to analyse the fate of these flavonoids in the
99 mice gastrointestinal tract (stomach, small intestine, colon, and cecum) and faeces.

100

101 **2. Material and methods**

102 **2.1 Chemicals**

103 Phloroglucinol and standards of (+)-catechin, (-)-epicatechin, procyanidin B2,
104 caffeic acid and apigenin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St.Louis, MO, USA).
105 Stock solutions at a concentration of 2000 mg/L for each phenolic were first prepared in
106 methanol and then serially diluted to working concentrations. Methanol and acetonitrile
107 were supplied from J. T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands), formic acid, HCl and
108 sodium acetate from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) and acetic acid from Scharlau
109 (Barcelona, Spain). Ascorbic acid was from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium). All other
110 chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Milli-Q system (Millipore Corp.,
111 Bedford, MA, USA) ultrapure water was used throughout the study.

112

113 **2.2. Preparation of Cupuassu Phenolic Extract (CPE)**

114 Cupuassu frozen pulp was obtained from *Tentação Amazônica* (Parauapebas,
115 Pará State, Brazil), a Brazilian producer that manufactures fruits of the Amazonian
116 region. Commercial cupuassu pulp (100 g fresh weight) was extracted three times with
117 a solvent mixture (200 mL the first time, 100 mL the next two times) comprising
118 methanol/water/acetic acid (70/29.5/0.5, v/v/v) in an Ultraturrax equipment (Polytron-
119 Kinematica GmbH, Kriens-Luzern, Sweden) at 24000 rpm for 1 min. The extract was
120 filtered under reduced pressure through filter paper (Whatman no. 1) and then
121 concentrated to remove methanol on a rotatory evaporator (Rotavapor RE 120; Büchi,
122 Flawil, Switzerland) at 40 °C. The aqueous phase was filtered through a reverse phase
123 C-18 cartridge (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA), previously activated with methanol
124 and water, in order to retain phenolic compounds and remove other highly hydrophilic
125 compounds. The phenolic compounds retained in each cartridge were eluted with
126 methanol. The collected methanolic fraction was evaporated to dryness and then
127 dissolved in distilled water (50 mL). Ten milliliters of the extract were used for
128 determination of phenolic contents by Folin-Ciocalteu method and for the *in vivo* study.
129 The other 40 mL of the extract were then freeze-dried for posterior extract
130 characterization analysis. The yield of cupuassu phenolic extract (40 mL) was 20 mg
131 dried weight.

132

133 **2.3 Total Phenolic Contents**

134 The phenolic content was determined according to a previous method
135 (Singleton, Orthofer, & Lamuela-Raventós, 1999). A 0.25 mL aliquot of CPE was
136 mixed with 0.25 mL of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2 mL of distilled water. After 3
137 min at room temperature, 0.25 mL of a saturated sodium carbonate solution was added
138 and the mixture placed at 37 °C in a water bath for 30 min. The absorbance was
139 measured at 750 nm using a model Ultrospec 2000 UV-visible spectrophotometer
140 (Amersham Biosciences, Cambridge, UK). The results were expressed as mg of
141 catechin equivalents (CE) per mL of extract. The total amount of polyphenols measured
142 by the Folin Ciocalteu (0.45 mg catechin equivalents (CE)/mL of the extract) was used
143 to calculate the dose to each mouse, considering the body weight of the animals.

144

145 **2.4 Characterization of cupuassu phenolic extract by HPLC-DAD-IT (MS/MS)**

146 **2.4.1 Analysis of phenolic compounds by HPLC-DAD-IT (MS/MS)**

147 The dried CPE (10 mg) was res-suspended in 1 mL of methanol/ water (80:20,
148 v/v) with 0.1% formic acid. After vortexing (1 min) and standing in an ultrasonic bath
149 for 10 min, the solution was centrifuged at 13000 g for 10 min and the supernatant
150 filtered through a 0.22 µm PVDF filter. Samples were analysed using an Agilent HPLC
151 1200 series instrument equipped with a diode array detector (Agilent Technologies,
152 Waldbronn, Germany) and an ion-trap mass spectrometer detector in series (Bruker
153 Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). Separation of phenolic compounds was achieved on a
154 reverse-phase C18 Pursuit XRs column (Agilent Technologies, Aldbronn, Germany)
155 (250 × 4 mm; 5 µm particle size). The mobile phase was water/formic acid (99:1, v/v)
156 (solvent A) and HPLC grade acetonitrile (solvent B), at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min.
157 Elution was performed with a gradient starting with 5% B in A, to reach 12% B in A at
158 10 min, 25% B in A at 20 min, 35% B in A at 30 min, 70% B in A at 35 min, 90% B in
159 A at 36 min and then became isocratic for 5 min. UV chromatograms were recorded at
160 280 and 340 nm. Nitrogen was used as drying and nebulizing gas in the electrospray
161 interface (ESI) with pressure at 65 psi, flow 11 L/min and temperature of 350 °C. Mass
162 scan (MS) and daughter (MS– MS) spectra were measured from m/z 100 up to m/z 800.
163 Collision-induced fragmentation experiments were performed in the ion trap using
164 helium as the collision gas, with voltage ramping cycles from 0.3 up to 2 V. Mass
165 spectrometry data were acquired in the negative mode. Clovamide was quantified with

166 the calibration curve of caffeic acid (1–1000 mg/L) at 280 nm and flavones (hypolaetin
167 and isoscutellarein derivatives) with the calibration curve of apigenin (1–500 mg/L) at
168 340 nm. All the samples and standards were injected in triplicate.

169

170 **2.4.2 Analysis of proanthocyanidins by phloroglucinolysis**

171 Proanthocyanidins were quantified as previously reported (Jakobek, García-
172 Villalba, & Tomás-Barberán, 2013; Pugliese et al., 2013). Briefly, a solution of 0.1 M
173 HCl in methanol containing 50 g/L of phloroglucinol and 10 g/L of ascorbic acid was
174 prepared. Nine milligrams of dried CPE were reacted with the phloroglucinolysis
175 reagent (150 μ L) in a water bath, for 20 min at 50 °C. The reaction was stopped by
176 placing the vials in ice and adding 150 μ L of 40 mM sodium acetate. The sample was
177 centrifuged and filtered through a 0.22 μ m PVDF filter prior to the injection. For the
178 analysis of these samples, the same HPLC–DAD–IT equipment described with the same
179 instrumental parameters previously reported (Jakobek et al., 2013; Pugliese et al., 2013)
180 were used. For the quantitation of total flavan-3-ols (flavan-3-ol monomers and
181 phloroglucinol adducts) catechin was used as quantitative standard (1–2000 mg/L). To
182 calculate the apparent mean degree of polymerization (mDP), the sum of all subunits
183 (flavan-3-ol monomer and phloroglucinol adducts, in moles) was divided by the sum of
184 all flavan-3-ol monomers (in moles).

185

186 **2.5 Animals and experimental design**

187 The study was approved by the Ethics Committee on Animal Experimentation of
188 the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of São Paulo, according to the
189 guidelines of the Brazilian College on Animal Experimentation (protocol number 353).
190 Twenty-seven male C57BL/6 mice (8 weeks old, 22–28 g body weight) were fed
191 Nuvilab CR-1 diets (Nuvital Nutrientes SA, Paraná, Brazil) and water *ad libitum* and
192 were kept under standard laboratory conditions of temperature (23 ± 2 °C), relative
193 humidity ($50 \pm 5\%$) and 12 h light-dark cycle. For the study, mice were later kept under
194 fasting conditions for 6 h prior to administration by gavage of a single dose of aqueous
195 CPE containing 5 mg of catechin equivalents/kg of body weight (b.w.). This amount is
196 equivalent to 350 mg of polyphenols for a 70-kg person per day or about 4 glasses of
197 juice made with commercial frozen pulp. This intake level of polyphenols is close to
198 those derived from the consumption of cocoa products in some European countries

199 (Zanotti et al., 2015) and is easily reached through diet. Tissue samples (stomach,
200 intestine, colon and cecum) were collected at 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 12 and 24 h after
201 dosing (3 mice per time). The tissues were weighed, immediately frozen in liquid
202 nitrogen and stored at -80 °C. Faeces were collected at 0, 3, 4, 6 and 12 h after dosing
203 and stored at -80 °C. All the samples were then freeze-dried for further phenolic
204 extraction and chromatographic analysis.

205

206 **2.6 Sample preparation**

207 Freeze dried samples of stomach, intestine, colon, cecum and faeces were
208 weighted (between 20 and 100 mg), and then extracted with methanol/ water (80:20,
209 v/v) plus 0.1% formic acid (at least 1 mL of extraction solvent per 50 mg of tissue
210 sample). The mixture was vortexed for 2 min followed by an ultrasonic bath for 10 min
211 and then centrifuged at 3000 g for 10 min. The supernatant was filtered (0.22 µm PVDF
212 filter) prior to the analysis.

213

214 **2.7 UPLC-ESI-QTOF analysis of tissue samples and faeces**

215 Tissue samples and faeces were analysed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity UPLC
216 system coupled to the 6550 Accurate-Mass quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometer
217 (QTOF) (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) using an electrospray interface
218 with Jet Stream technology. Separation was achieved on a reverse phase Poroshell 120
219 EC-C18 column (3 × 100 mm, 2.7 µm; Agilent) operating at 30 °C. The mobile phases
220 were water/ formic acid (99.9:0.1 v/v; phase A) and ACN/ formic acid (99.9:0.1 v/v;
221 phase B). Gradient program was as follows: 0–4 min, 5–18% B; 4–15 min, 18–30% B;
222 15–20 min, 30– 90% B, 1 min at 90% and then back to the initial conditions in 1 min
223 and the column was equilibrated for 5 min. The flow rate was set constant at 0.4
224 mL/min and the injection volume was 3 µL. The optimal conditions of the electrospray
225 interface were as follows: gas temperature 280 °C, drying gas 9 L/min, nebulizer 45 psi,
226 sheath gas temperature 400 °C, sheath gas flow 12 L/min. Spectra were acquired in
227 single MS mode with *m/z* range of 100–1100, negative polarity, and an acquisition rate
228 of 1.5 spectra/s. Continuous internal calibration was performed in the analyses using
229 two reference masses (112.9855 and 1033.9881). A target screening strategy was
230 applied to all the samples for the identification of possibly derived metabolites. This
231 strategy consists of searching for a list of potential biotransformation products after MS
232 full acquisition to generate a series of extracted ion chromatograms (EICs). The

233 screening was based on mass filtering at the exact mass of the compound investigated
234 using narrow mass extraction windows (0.01 m/z). This list was created taking into
235 account the original compounds present in the extracts and the information available in
236 the literature about the microbial metabolism of flavonoids (Liang et al., 2014; Marín et
237 al., 2015; Monagas et al., 2010; Stanoeva & Stefova, 2013). A theoretical metabolic
238 pathway was proposed for the flavones (hypolaetin and isoscutellarein) and flavan-3-ols
239 (epicatechin) (**Supplementary Figures 1 and 2**). All the metabolites proposed in these
240 routes along with hydroxylated, methylated, glucuronidated and sulphated conjugates
241 were searched in the targeted analysis. These EICs were compared between control and
242 treated samples to eliminate those chromatographic peaks that also appeared in the
243 control samples.

244 Due to the absence of available standards, the distribution of parent compounds and
245 metabolites along the GI was studied using the area under the curve of the different
246 compounds. Peak areas obtained using extracted ion chromatograms (EIC) was
247 corrected with the ratio: milligrams of tissue (dry weight)/quantity of solvent used
248 during the extraction of each sample. Although the quantitative comparison between
249 compounds was not possible, using corrected area enables to plot the evolution of each
250 compound along the different tissues of the gastrointestinal tract.

251

252 **3 Results and Discussion**

253 **3.1 Analysis of Cupuassu Phenolic Extract (CPE)**

254 Identification and peak assignment of the native phenolic compounds present in
255 CPE were based on the comparison of their retention times and UV and mass spectral
256 data with those of standards and previously published data (Pugliese et al., 2013; Yang
257 et al., 2003). In total, 7 compounds were detected by HPLC-DAD-ESI-MS/MS
258 chromatogram (**Figure 2**) and their characteristics and content in cupuassu phenolic
259 extract are shown in **Table 1**.

260 As described by Pugliese et al. (2013), glucuronide and sulpho-glucuronide
261 derivatives of hypolaetin (peaks **2** and **5**), hypolaethin-3'-methyl ether (peaks **4** and **7**)
262 and isoscutellarein (peaks **3** and **6**) were identified with maxima of absorption around
263 340 nm and the same fragmentation profiles previously reported for these compounds
264 (**Table 1**). The total amount of flavones was 87.48 ± 0.38 mg/g d.w., being hypolaetin
265 8-O- β -D glucuronide and isoscutellarein 8-O- β -D glucuronide 3''-sulphate the

266 predominant ones. Hypolaetin and isoscutellarein are not common dietary flavones and
267 have only been previously found as different glycosidic conjugates in different plants
268 (*Sideritis* spp. *Gratiola* spp. and the liverwort *Bucegia*) (Tomás-Barberán et al., 1987;
269 Grayer-Barkmeijer & Tomás-Barberán, 1993).

270 Clovamide (Peak 1, λ max = 280 nm), a polyphenolic amide previously reported
271 in cocoa (Arlorio et al., 2008) was identified for the first time in cupuassu extract. The
272 presence of the parent ion at m/z 358 and the same daughter ions at m/z 222, 178, 161
273 and 133, previously reported in the literature (Arlorio et al., 2008), confirmed its
274 identification. Clovamide was present at a concentration of 23.03 ± 0.25 mg/g d.w.

275 In addition, peaks of epicatechin and procyanidin B2 were detected but only in
276 MS. More accurate quantitation of proanthocyanidins was done using
277 phloroglucinolysis (**Table 2**). Epicatechin and catechin were present as terminal units in
278 the proanthocyanidin oligomers but epicatechin was 13 times more abundant than
279 catechin. As previously reported (Pugliese et al., 2013), the extension units were only
280 epicatechin. The total content was 63 mg epicatechin equivalents/g of CPE d.w., and the
281 mean degree of polymerization was around 2.

282 These results show that despite their phylogenetic proximity, cocoa and
283 cupuassu have differences in their phenolic composition. Both are known to have high
284 levels of flavan-3-ols and procyanidins (Cucaita et al., 2014; Oliveira & Genovese,
285 2013) but cupuassu contains also a mixture of glucuronide and sulpho-glucuronide
286 derivatives of the flavones hypolaetin, isoscutellarein and hypolaetin methyl ether that
287 are not found in cocoa (**Figure 1**).

288 These polyphenols have been described as potential health promoters, although
289 it is known that some health benefits derived from polyphenol consumption depend on
290 their bioaccessibility in the gastrointestinal tract and on the close contact with the gut
291 microbiota (Cardona et al., 2013; Selma et al., 2009). Therefore, the gastrointestinal
292 tract was chosen as the primary target to evaluate the distribution and microbial
293 metabolic conversion of this unique combination of flavonoids present in cupuassu.

294

295 **3.2. Identification and distribution of parent compounds in the GI along the time**

296 The list of parent compounds (P) detected in the gastrointestinal tissues and
297 faeces is presented in **Table 3A**. Compounds were tentatively identified taking into
298 account the molecular formula generated with high scores (≥ 90) and low errors (≤ 2.5

299 ppm). In addition, information on the fragmentation pattern was very useful to support
300 the identification.

301 As can be observed in **Table 3A**, the major fragment ion of procyanidin B2 (**P1**)
302 was m/z 289 corresponding to the monomer epicatechin. Epicatechin (**P2**) and
303 clovamide (**P3**) showed characteristic fragmentation patterns in agreement with those
304 found in the literature (Arlorio et al., 2008; Cádiz-Gurrea et al., 2014). The MS² of
305 glucuronides (**P4, P6, P7**) showed fragment ions at m/z 175 and others corresponding to
306 the aglycones (m/z 301, 315 or 285). Sulpho-glucuronide derivatives (**P5, P8, P9**)
307 showed fragments at [M-80] and [M-80-176] indicating the sequential loss of the
308 sulphate and glucuronide to lead to the aglycone molecule. The sulpho-glucuronide
309 fragment at m/z 255 was also observed. Flavone glucuronide and sulpho-glucuronide
310 conjugates (**P4-P9**) detected in the gastrointestinal samples showed the same retention
311 time that those found in the extract, indicating that the same ingested compounds were
312 accumulated along the gastrointestinal tract and no transformation to other isomers was
313 produced. **Figure 3A** illustrates EIC chromatogram of the main parent compounds
314 detected in stomach 0.5 h after the administration of the CPE.

315 The distribution of the parent compounds in gastrointestinal tract along time is
316 shown in **Figure 4**. Despite the high variability of the results, a clear tendency could be
317 observed. Results showed that clovamide decreased in the gastric lumen over time
318 reaching maxima at 0.5 h in the stomach, 1 h in the small intestine, 2 h in the cecum and
319 3 h in the colon (**Figure 4A**). A similar behaviour was observed for epicatechin and
320 proanthocyanidin B2 (**Figure 4B and 4C**) although in both cases the amount increased
321 in the small intestine between 0.5 and 2 hours, probably because of the partial
322 hydrolysis of proanthocyanidin oligomers to dimers and monomers. Despite the
323 controversial reports regarding the release of monomers from oligomers in the
324 gastrointestinal tract, the hydrolysis of procyanidin polymers in the stomach has been
325 previously reported (Margalef, Pons, Bravo, Muguerza, & Arola-Arnal, 2015; Spencer,
326 2003). The highest amounts of these three parent compounds were detected in the
327 stomach and the small intestine and then decreased in the rest of the gastrointestinal
328 tract.

329 Regarding the flavones present in the extract, the evolution of hypolaetin
330 glucuronide and hypolaetin glucuronide-sulphate along the GI tract is shown in **Figures**
331 **4D and 4E**, respectively. A similar behaviour was observed for conjugates of the other
332 two flavones (hypolaetin methyl ether and isoscutellarein). Glucuronide derivatives

333 were found in the stomach and the small intestine with a residence time of around 2-3
334 hours. Their absence from cecum and colon could indicate either a fast absorption at the
335 intestinal level to reach the blood stream or degradation in the colon to generate their
336 aglycones and other microbial metabolites. In the case of sulpho-glucuronides, large
337 amounts were detected in cecum 3 h after supplementation, probably because of the
338 enterohepatic circulation (Dai et al., 2015).

339 The accumulation of parent compounds during some hours in the tissues could
340 exert local effects that would contribute to their health benefits. In particular, their
341 presence in small intestine could interfere with key signalling and metabolic pathways
342 with potential benefits to the host (García-Conesa, 2015). The inhibition of gut digestive
343 enzyme activities, as well the modulation of receptors and nutrient transporters, have
344 been described as adjuvants in the treatment of the alterations in glucose and lipids
345 homeostasis (García-Conesa, 2015; Williamson, 2013). Previous studies showed that a
346 cupuassu extract displayed a potent inhibition of α -amylase activity (Gonçalves et al.,
347 2010) and that some flavones also had strong inhibitory activity of α -glucosidase (Li et
348 al., 2009; Xiao, 2015), while flavan-3-ols apparently had stronger lipase inhibitory
349 activity compared to other classes of polyphenols (Gonzales et al., 2015). In addition,
350 flavan-3-ols have also the potential to modulate incretins as glucagon-like peptide-1
351 (GLP-1) and dipeptidyl-peptidase 4 (DPP4) activity *in vitro* (Gonzalez-Abuín et al.,
352 2014), and reduce sugar absorption through the inhibition of the main transporters of
353 glucose present in the intestinal epithelial cells (Williamson, 2013). Therefore, previous
354 beneficial effects attributed to the presence of phenolic compounds in cupuassu
355 (Oliveira & Genovese, 2013; Oliveira et al., 2015), as the improvement of glucose
356 tolerance and dyslipidaemia, could be partly attributed to the modulation of these
357 described metabolic pathways. However, further studies are necessary to confirm this
358 hypothesis *in vivo*.

359

360 **3.3. Identification and distribution of microbial metabolites in the GI along the** 361 **time.**

362 The decrease in cecum and colon of the CPE parent compounds could be due to
363 their transformation to microbial metabolites by the colonic microbiota. As has been
364 widely reported, most of the proanthocyanidins and flavonoids consumed in the diet are
365 unabsorbed and reach the colon where they are transformed by the resident microbiota
366 (Marín et al., 2015; Selma et al., 2009). A targeted metabolic analysis was carried out

367 searching for all the possible microbial metabolites derived from flavones (hypolaetin
368 and isoscutellarein) and flavan-3-ols (epicatechin) (theoretical metabolic pathways were
369 depicted in **Supplementary Figures 1 and 2**). Finally, the microbial metabolites (M)
370 identified in the gastrointestinal tissues and faeces with a high score (≥ 90) and low
371 errors (≤ 2.5 ppm) are shown in **Table 3B**. **Figure 3B** illustrates EIC chromatogram of
372 the main microbial metabolites detected in colon 4 h after the administration of the
373 CPE.

374

375 **3.3.1. Microbial metabolism of flavones present in CPE.**

376 Comparing to other flavonoids, there are few studies considering microbial
377 metabolism of flavones and in particular of the 5,7,8-OH flavones present in CPE.
378 Although scarce, data about microbial transformation of flavones (i.e. apigenin)
379 (Schoefer, Mohan, Schwiertz, Braune, & Blaut, 2003; Hanske, Loh, Sczesny, Blaut, &
380 Braune, 2009) and other families of flavonoids were useful to depict a theoretical
381 metabolic pathway for hypolaetin and isoscutellarein (**Supplementary Figure 1**). After
382 an exhaustive search of all the proposed metabolites and their conjugates, only flavone
383 aglycones (hypolaetin (**M9**), isoscutellarein (**M10**) and hypolaetin methyl ether (**M11**),
384 characterized by a fragment ion at [M-168], were identified (**Figure 1**). No extensive
385 metabolism to other smaller phenolic acids was found, showing poor colonic
386 fermentation of this group of flavones.

387 This was in accordance with data previously published for the metabolism of
388 scutellarin (scutellarein-7-O- β -D glucuronide), the main active compound from
389 *Erigeron breviscapus* extract, which was hydrolysed into scutellarein by β -
390 glucuronidase from the gastrointestinal bacteria (Tang et al., 2014; Wang, Xia, Liu, Qiu,
391 & Di, 2014). In another study, the urinary excretion of glucuronide conjugates of
392 flavones after ingestion of a cup of mountain tea (*Sideritis scardica*), in which the
393 dominant flavonoids are glucosides of hypolaetin and isoscutellarein, also support our
394 results (Stanoeva & Stefova 2013).

395 The same metabolic behaviour was observed for baicalein and wogonoside,
396 flavones with similar A-ring structure as those from cupuassu, that are present as
397 glucuronide conjugates in the rhizome of the medicinal plant *Scutellaria baicalensis*.
398 These compounds are poorly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract in its native form
399 and are hydrolysed by intestinal microflora into their aglycones in humans and rats
400 (Kang et al., 2014; Xing, Wang, Peng, Chen, & Li, 2014). Reductions of the double

401 bond, methylations and hydroxylations have also been suggested in the catabolic
402 pathways of baicalein (Du et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015). However, as occurred with
403 the flavones in CPE, degradation into low molecular weight phenolic acids through the
404 cleavage of the C-ring has not been described. All these flavones have in common the
405 presence of three phenolic hydroxyl groups in the A-ring, a chemical feature that
406 somehow could affect the fission of the heterocyclic C-ring. Further research would be
407 needed to test this hypothesis.

408 The distribution of the flavone aglycones along the gastrointestinal tract is
409 shown in **Figure 4F**. As can be observed, aglycones that were not originally present in
410 the extracts were first detected in the stomach. This suggests partial hydrolysis of the
411 flavone conjugates at this level by microbial populations that have been described to be
412 higher in the stomach of rodents than in that of humans (Day et al., 2000). However,
413 aglycones just appeared in one of the three mice analyzed at the different times,
414 showing a high variability. More homogeneous results were observed in cecum and
415 colon with the highest concentration at 2 and 4 hours, respectively, showing the
416 implication of the gut microbiota in the transformation of flavone conjugates into their
417 aglycones.

418

419 **3.3.2. Microbial metabolism of the flava-3-ols and the procyanidins present in** 420 **CPE.**

421 Regarding monomeric flavan-3-ols and oligomeric procyanidins, their microbial
422 degradation pathway has been partially elucidated by numerous *in vitro* and *in vivo*
423 studies using pure standards as well as grapes, tea, cocoa, berries, red wines and their
424 extracts (Liang et al., 2014; Monagas et al., 2010; Van Duynhoven et al., 2013). Based
425 on the literature, a colonic degradation pathway was proposed (**Supplementary Figure**
426 **2**) and the target analysis was focused on searching for these metabolites.

427 Microbial metabolites derived from epicatechin were detected in cecum, colon
428 and faeces (**Table 3B**). Metabolite **M3**, with m/z 291.0874 (molecular formula
429 $C_{15}H_{16}O_6$) and characteristic fragments at m/z 247, 205, 167, 151, 135 and 123, was
430 identified as 1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-3-(2,4,6-trihydroxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (3,4-
431 diHPP-2-ol); and metabolite **M8**, with m/z 275.0925 and a molecular formula with one
432 oxygen less than the previous compound, was identified as 1-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(2, 4,
433 6-trihydroxyphenyl) propan-2-ol (3-HHP-2-ol). Metabolite **M5**, with m/z 207.0282
434 (molecular formula $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$) and characteristic fragments at m/z 175, 163, 143 and

435 122, was identified as 5-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl-valerolactone). Trace levels of
436 Metabolite **M7**, with molecular formula $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$, that was only present at trace levels,
437 was tentatively identified as 3,4-dihydroxyphenylvaleric acid. These compounds,
438 represented in **Figure 1**, were previously identified as (epi)catechin catabolic
439 metabolites, and the detected MS/MS fragments were consistent with those previously
440 reported (Appeldoorn et al., 2009; Kutschera, Engst, Blaut, & Braune, 2011; Liang et
441 al., 2014). Flavan-3-ol C-ring fission products (**M3**, **M5** and **M8**) appeared in the cecum
442 and colon 2 h after the ingestion and remained until 6 h with maxima around 2 -3 h in
443 the cecum and 3-4 h in the colon (**Supplementary Figure 3**). According to the
444 molecular formula and fragmentation pattern, metabolite **M4** was tentatively identified
445 as a sulphate derivative of 5-(3-hydroxyphenyl)- γ -valerolactone. In addition, a sulphate
446 derivative (**M1**) of the metabolite M2 was also suggested with molecular formula
447 $C_{17}H_{18}O_9S$ and a fragment at m/z 315 [M-82]. Both sulphate conjugates were also
448 detected in the small intestine (**Supplementary Figure 3**), suggesting that their
449 corresponding aglycones were probably absorbed into the colonocytes where it would
450 undergo extensive metabolism and then return to the intestinal lumen by enterohepatic
451 circulation as occurs with other flavonoids (Dai et al., 2015; Cardona et al., 2013; Chen
452 et al., 2014). Small amounts of all microbial metabolites appeared in faecal samples at
453 12 hours after supplementation.

454 The microbial metabolic profile obtained for flava-3-ols and procyanidins from
455 cupuassu was slightly different from those found after the intake of other procyanidin-
456 rich foods (Goodrich et al., 2014; Margalef et al., 2015). Hydroxyphenyl valeric acid
457 and valerolactone derivatives were previously identified as characteristic metabolites of
458 flavan-3-ols consumption; however in other matrixes, the colonic degradation reached
459 low molecular weight phenolic acids (hydroxyphenylacetic, hydroxyphenylpropionic
460 and hydroxybenzoic acids). For instance, after cocoa consumption, a product with
461 similar procyanidin pattern than cupuassu, 3,4-dihydroxyphenyl propionic acid, 3-
462 hydroxyphenyl acetic acid and phenylvalerolactones were found in rat urine (Urpi-Sarda
463 et al., 2009) and mainly hydroxybenzoic acids were quantified in mice gastrointestinal
464 tissues (Goodrich et al., 2014). These metabolites with lower molecular weights were
465 not found after CPE consumption. In contrast, diarylpropan-2-ol metabolites, the first
466 intermediate compounds formed after the fission of the heterocyclic C-ring, were
467 detected with high intensity. Diarylpropan-2-ol metabolites have been previously
468 described *in vitro* after incubation with human and rat intestinal bacteria (Kutschera et

469 al., 2011; Takagaki & Nanjo, 2010) but only two studies described their presence *in*
470 *vivo* after consumption of epicatechin gallate or catechin by rats (Liang et al., 2014;
471 Takagaki & Nanjo, 2010). Their absence in other studies was attributed to their fast
472 conversion to other metabolites.

473 It seems that a slower microbial metabolism has been produced in the presence
474 of CPE compared to other similar matrixes as cocoa products. This variation in
475 microbial metabolism could be the result from qualitative differences in the profile of
476 native flavan-3-ols or because of the presence in the extract of other polyphenols as
477 flavones, which could interfere with flavan-3-ols microbial metabolism. The two-way
478 interaction between microbiota and polyphenols has been recently described indicating
479 the modulatory capacity of these bioactive compounds on gut microbiota composition
480 (Cardona et al., 2013; Marín et al., 2015).

481 Native flavonoids and their microbial metabolites are retained for a period of
482 time (around 3 hours) in the colonic mucosa where they can exert their beneficial effects
483 including anti-inflammatory and anticarcinogenic activity, improved barrier function,
484 reduced permeability to lipopolysaccharides and modulation of the gut microflora
485 populations through selective prebiotic effects and antimicrobial activities (Celep et al.,
486 2014; Marín et al., 2015). Flavan-3-ol monomers and proanthocyanidins may favour
487 beneficial bacteria such as *Bifidobacterium*, *Enterococcus*, *Lactobacillus* spp. as well
488 increase butyrate production, but may also inhibit other groups such *Clostridium* spp.
489 and *Staphylococcus* spp. (Cardona et al., 2013; Tzounis et al., 2011). No studies about
490 hypolaetin and isoscutellarein effects on gut microbiota modulation have been
491 completed so far. However, another flavone, luteolin, showed antibacterial effects
492 against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. fluorescens* and *E. coli*. (Marín et al., 2015).

493

494 **3.3.3. Other unknown metabolites**

495 Other metabolites were detected in cecum, colon and faeces samples after the
496 administration of the CPE, although precise identification was not achieved. **M2** and
497 **M6** with molecular formula $C_{17}H_{18}O_6$ and $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$ and fragmentation patterns similar
498 to that found for 3,4-diHPP-2-ol (m/z 151, 135, 123 and 109) could be considered
499 derivatives of epicatechin ($C_{15}H_{14}O_6$) with two extra methyl groups in M2 and an
500 additional hydroxyl group in M6. However, both compounds could be also considered
501 degradation products of flavones originated by hydrogenation, C-ring opening and
502 subsequent demethylation. A tentative structure for the metabolite with molecular

503 formula $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$ is shown in **Supplementary Figure 1**. More knowledge about the
504 identity of these unknown compounds and the position of the extra-groups could not be
505 achieved with the information available. Unknown metabolite **M2** remained in cecum
506 and colon between 3 and 6 h and metabolite **M6** showed it highest concentration 3 h
507 after the supplementation (**Supplementary Figure 3**).

508

509

510 **4. Conclusions**

511 Gastrointestinal distribution and microbial metabolic conversion of a unique
512 combination of flavonoids (flavan-3-ols, procyanidins and flavones) present in cupuassu
513 phenolic extract (CPE) were studied. Naturally occurring compounds were mainly
514 accumulated in the stomach and small intestine where they could exert local effects. The
515 decrease observed of the CPE compounds in cecum and colon could be linked to their
516 transformation to microbial metabolites by the colonic bacteria. Flavones present as
517 glucuronides were mainly hydrolyzed into their respective aglycones, hypolaetin,
518 isoscutellarein and hypolaethin methylether. Microbial metabolism of procyanidins
519 from CPE was different from that observed in other similar procyanidin-containing
520 products as is the case of cocoa. They were mainly transformed to diarylpropan-2-ol
521 metabolites, 5-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- γ -valerolactone and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylvaleric
522 acid. For both families of flavonoids, no further metabolism to render smaller phenolic
523 acids was observed. The qualitative profile of microbial metabolites could be affected
524 by the presence in the matrix of different polyphenols that could modulate the
525 flavonoid-degrading gut microbiota.

526

527

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

528 We thank *Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico* (CNPq
529 162218/2011-7) and *Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior*
530 (CAPES 99999.003759/2014-08) for financial support.

531

532

533

534

REFERENCES

535

536 Appeldoorn, M. M., Vincken, J. P., Aura, A.-M., Hollman, P. C. H., & Gruppen, H.
537 (2009). Procyanidin dimers are metabolized by human microbiota with 2-(3,4-
538 dihydroxyphenyl)acetic acid and 5-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- γ -valerolactone as the
539 major metabolites. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *57*, 1084–1092.

540 Arlorio, M., Locatelli, M., Travaglia, F., Coisson, J. D., Del Grosso, E., Minassi, A.,
541 Appendino, G., & Martelli, A. (2008). Roasting impact on the contents of
542 clovamide (*N*-caffeoyl-*L*-DOPA) and the antioxidant activity of cocoa beans
543 (*Theobroma cacao* L.). *Food Chemistry*, *106*, 967–975.

544 Cádiz-Gurrea, M. L., Lozano-Sanchez, J., Contreras-Gómez, M., Legeai-Mallet, L.,
545 Fernández-Arroyo, S., & Segura-Carretero, A. (2014). Isolation, comprehensive
546 characterization and antioxidant activities of *Theobroma cacao* extract. *Journal of*
547 *Functional Foods*, *10*, 485–498.

548 Cardona, F., Andrés-Lacueva, C., Tulipani, S., Tinahones, F. J., & Queipo-Ortuño, M. I.
549 (2013). Benefits of polyphenols on gut microbiota and implications in human
550 health. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, *24*, 1415–1422.

551 Celep, G. S., Rastmanesh, R., & Marotta, F. (2014). Microbial metabolism of
552 polyphenols and health. In R. R. Watson, V. R. Preedy, & S. Zibadi (Eds),
553 *Polyphenols in human health and disease* (pp. 577–589). Elsevier.

554 Chen, Z., Zheng, S., Li, L., & Jiang, H. (2014). Metabolism of flavonoids in human : A
555 comprehensive review. *Current Drug Metabolism*, *15*, 48–61.

556 Cucaita, N. A., Hernández, M. S., & Gutiérrez, R. H. (2014). Comparison between
557 chocolate and an analog product made from copoazú (*Theobroma grandiflorum*).
558 *Acta Horticulturae*, *1047*, 231–236.

559 Dai, P., Zhu, L., Luo, F., Lu, L., Li, Q., Wang, L., Wang, X., Hu, M., & Liu, Z. (2015).
560 Triple recycling processes impact systemic and local bioavailability of orally
561 administered flavonoids. *The American Association of Pharmaceutical Scientists*
562 *Journal*, *17*, 723–736.

563 Day, A. J., Cañada, F. J., Díaz, J. C., Kroon, P. A., McLauchlan, R., Faulds, C. B.,
564 Plumb, G. W., Morgan, M. R., & Williamson, G. (2000). Dietary flavonoid and
565 isoflavone glycosides are hydrolysed by the lactase site of lactase phlorizin
566 hydrolase. *Federation of European Biochemical Societies Letters*, *468*, 166–170.

567 Du, L., Qian, D., Shang, E., Liu, P., Jiang, S., Guo, J., Su, S., Duan, J., Xu, J., & Zhao,
568 M. (2015). UPLC-Q-TOF/MS-based screening and identification of the main
569 flavonoids and their metabolites in rat bile, urine and feces after oral administration
570 of *Scutellaria baicalensis* extract. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, *169*, 156–162.

571 García-Conesa, M.T. (2015). Dietary polyphenols against metabolic disorders: how far

- 572 have we progressed in the understanding of the molecular mechanisms of action of
573 these compounds? *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, (in press).
- 574 Gonçalves, A. E. S. S., Lajolo, F. M., & Genovese, M. I. (2010). Chemical composition
575 and antioxidant/antidiabetic potential of brazilian native fruits and commercial
576 frozen pulps. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *58*, 4666–4674.
- 577 Gonzales, G. B., Smaghe, G., Grootaert, C., Zotti, M., Raes, K., & Camp, J. Van.
578 (2015). Flavonoid interactions during digestion, absorption, distribution and
579 metabolism: a sequential structure–activity/property relationship-based approach in
580 the study of bioavailability and bioactivity. *Drug Metabolism Reviews*, *47*, 1–16.
- 581 Gonzalez-Abuin, N., Pinent, M., Casanova-Marti, A., Arola, L., Blay, M., & Ardevol,
582 A. (2014). Procyanidins and their healthy protective effects against type 2 diabetes.
583 *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, *22*, 39–50.
- 584 Goodrich, K. M., Dorenkott, M. R., Ye, L., O’Keefe, S. F., Hulver, M. W., & Neilson,
585 A. P. (2014). Dietary supplementation with cocoa flavanols does not alter colon
586 tissue profiles of native flavanols and their microbial metabolites established
587 during habitual dietary exposure in C57BL/6J mice. *Journal of Agricultural and*
588 *Food Chemistry*, *62*, 11190–11199.
- 589 Grayer-Barkmeijer, R. J., & Tomás-Barberán, F. A. (1993). 8-Hydroxylated flavone O-
590 glycosides and other flavonoids in chemotypes of *Gratiola officinalis*.
591 *Phytochemistry*, *34*, 205–210.
- 592 Hanske, L., Loh, G., Sczesny, S., Blaut, M., & Braune, A. (2009). The bioavailability of
593 apigenin-7-glucoside is influenced by human intestinal microbiota in rats. *Journal*
594 *of Nutrition*, *139*, 1095–1102.
- 595 Jakobek, L., García-Villalba, R., & Tomás-Barberán, F. A. (2013). Polyphenolic
596 characterisation of old local apple varieties from Southeastern European region.
597 *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, *31*, 199–211.
- 598 Kang, M. J., Ko, G. S., Oh, D. G., Kim, J. S., Noh, K., Kang, W., Yoon, W. K., Kim, H.
599 C., Jeong, H. G., & Jeong, T. C. (2014). Role of metabolism by intestinal
600 microbiota in pharmacokinetics of oral baicalin. *Archives of Pharmacal Research*,
601 *37*, 371–378.
- 602 Kutschera, M., Engst, W., Blaut, M., & Braune, A. (2011). Isolation of catechin-
603 converting human intestinal bacteria. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, *111*, 165–
604 175.
- 605 Li, H., Song, F., Xing, J., Tsao, R., Liu, Z., & Liu, S. (2009). Screening and structural
606 characterization of α -glucosidase inhibitors from hawthorn leaf flavonoids extract
607 by ultrafiltration LC-DAD-MSⁿ and SORI-CID FTICR MS. *Journal of the*
608 *American Society for Mass Spectrometry*, *20*, 1496–1503.

- 609 Liang, J., Xu, F., Zhang, Y. Z., Zang, X. Y., Wang, D., Shang, M. Y., Wang, X.,
610 Chui, D. H., & Cai, S. Q. (2014). The profiling and identification of the metabolites
611 of (+)-catechin and study on their distribution in rats by HPLC-DAD-ESI-IT-TOF-
612 MSⁿ technique. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 28(3), 401–411.
- 613 Lim, T. K. (2012). *Theobroma grandiflorum*. In *Edible medicinal and non medicinal*
614 *plants* (pp. 252–258). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- 615 Margalef, M., Pons, Z., Bravo, F. I., Muguera, B., & Arola-Arnal, A. (2015). Tissue
616 distribution of rat flavanol metabolites at different doses. *The Journal of*
617 *Nutritional Biochemistry*, 26, 987–995.
- 618 Marín, L., Miguélez, E. M., Villar, C. J., & Lombó, F. (2015). Bioavailability of dietary
619 polyphenols and gut microbiota metabolism: antimicrobial properties. *BioMed*
620 *Research International*, 1–18.
- 621 Monagas, M., Urpi-Sarda, M., Sánchez-Patán, F., Llorach, R., Garrido, I., Gómez-
622 Cordovés, C., Andres-Lacueva, C., & Bartolomé, B. (2010). Insights into the
623 metabolism and microbial biotransformation of dietary flavan-3-ols and the
624 bioactivity of their metabolites. *Food & Function*, 1, 233–253.
- 625 Oliveira, T. B., & Genovese, M. I. (2013). Chemical composition of cupuassu
626 (*Theobroma grandiflorum*) and cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*) liquors and their effects
627 on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Food Research International*, 51, 929–935.
- 628 Oliveira, T. B., Rogero, M. M., & Genovese, M. I. (2015). Polyphenolic-rich extracts
629 from cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) and cupuassu (*Theobroma grandiflorum* Willd.
630 Ex Spreng. K. Shum) liquors: A comparison of metabolic effects in high-fat fed
631 rats. *PharmaNutrition*, 3, 20–28.
- 632 Pinent, M., Castell-Auví, A., Genovese, M. I., Serrano, J., Casanova, A., Blay, M., &
633 Ardévol, A. (2015). Antioxidant effects of proanthocyanidin-rich natural extracts
634 from grape seed and cupuassu on gastrointestinal mucosa. *Journal of the Science of*
635 *Food and Agriculture*, 96, 178–182.
- 636 Pugliese, A. G., Tomás-Barberán, F. A., Truchado, P., & Genovese, M. I. (2013).
637 Flavonoids, proanthocyanidins, vitamin c, and antioxidant activity of *Theobroma*
638 *grandiflorum* (Cupuassu) Pulp and Seeds. *Journal of Agricultural and Food*
639 *Chemistry*, 61, 2720–2728.
- 640 Rabadan-Chavez, G., Quevedo-Corona, L., Millar-García, A., Reyes-Maldonado, E., &
641 Jaramillo-Flores, M. E. (2016). Cocoa powder, cocoa extract and epicatechin
642 attenuate hypercaloric diet-induced obesity through enhanced β -oxidation and
643 energy expenditure in white adipose tissue. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 20, 54-
644 67.
- 645 Rein, M. J., Renouf, M., Cruz-Hernandez, C., Actis-Goretta, L., Thakkar, S. K., & da
646 Silva Pinto, M. (2013). Bioavailability of bioactive food compounds: a challenging

- 647 journey to bioefficacy. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 75, 588–602.
- 648 Santos, G. M., Maia, G. A., Sousa, P. H. M., Figueiredo, R. W., Costa, J. M. C., &
649 Fonseca, A. V. V. (2010). Atividade antioxidante e correlações com componentes
650 bioativos de produtos comerciais de cupuaçu. *Ciência Rural*, 40, 1636–1642.
- 651 Schoefer, L., Mohan, R., Schwiertz, A., Braune, A., & Blaut, M. (2003). Anaerobic
652 degradation of flavonoids by *Clostridium orbiscindens*. *Applied and Environmental*
653 *Microbiology*, 69, 5849–5854.
- 654 Selma, M. V., Espín, J. C., & Tomás-Barberán, F. a. (2009). Interaction between
655 phenolics and gut microbiota: role in human health. *Journal of Agricultural and*
656 *Food Chemistry*, 57, 6485–6501.
- 657 Singleton, V. L., Orthofer, R., & Lamuela-Raventós, R. M. (1999). Analysis of total
658 phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu
659 reagent. *Methods in Enzymology*, 299, 152–178.
- 660 Smith, D. F. (2013). Benefits of flavanol-rich cocoa-derived products for mental well-
661 being: A Review. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 5, 10-15.
- 662 Spencer, J. P. E. (2003). Role of flavonoids in the diet metabolism of tea flavonoids in
663 the gastrointestinal tract. *Journal of Nutrition*, 133, 3255S–3261S.
- 664 Stanoeva, J. P., & Stefova, M. (2013). Assay of urinary excretion of polyphenols after
665 ingestion of a cup of mountain tea (*Sideritis scardica*) measured by HPLC-DAD-
666 ESI-MS/MS. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 61, 10488–10497.
- 667 Takagaki, A., & Nanjo, F. (2010). Metabolism of (–)-epigallocatechin gallate by rat
668 intestinal flora. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 58, 1313–1321.
- 669 Tang, H., Li, N.-G., Tang, Y.-P., Shi, Q.-P., Guo, J.-M., Zhang, W., Shen, M. Z., &
670 Duan, J.-A. (2014). Identification of scutellarein metabolites in rat using ultra
671 performance liquid chromatography/quadrupole-time-of-flight mass spectrometry.
672 *Analytical Methods*, 6, 4667.
- 673 Tomás-Barberán, F. A. T., Mañez, S., & Villar, A. (1987). Identification of
674 antiinflammatory agents from sideritis species growing in Spain. *Journal of*
675 *Natural Products*, 50, 313–314.
- 676 Tzounis, X., Rodriguez-Mateos, A., Vulevic, J., Gibson, G. R., Kwik-Urbe, C., &
677 Spencer, J. P. (2011). Prebiotic evaluation of cocoa-derived flavanols in healthy
678 humans by using a randomized, controlled, double-blind, crossover intervention
679 study. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 93, 62–72.
- 680 Urpi-Sarda, M., Monagas, M., Khan, N., Lamuela-Raventós, R. M., Santos-Buelga, C.,
681 Sacanella, E., Castell, M., Permanyer, J., & Andres-Lacueva, C. (2009).
682 Epicatechin, procyanidins, and phenolic microbial metabolites after cocoa intake in
683 humans and rats. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 394, 1545–1556.

- 684 Van Duynhoven, J., Vaughan, E. E., van Dorsten, F., Gomez-Roldan, V., de Vos, R.,
685 Vervoort, J., Roger, L., Draijer, R., & Jacobs, D. M. (2013). Interactions of black
686 tea polyphenols with human gut microbiota: implications for gut and
687 cardiovascular health. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 98, 1631S–1641S.
- 688 Vriesmann, L. C., Silveira, J. L. M., & Petkowicz, C. L. D. O. (2010). Rheological
689 behavior of a pectic fraction from the pulp of cupuassu (*Theobroma grandiflorum*).
690 *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 79, 312–317.
- 691 Wang, X., Xia, H., Liu, Y., Qiu, F., & Di, X. (2014). Simultaneous determination of
692 three glucuronide conjugates of scutellarein in rat plasma by LC–MS/MS for
693 pharmacokinetic study of breviscapine. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 965, 79–84.
- 694 Williamson, G. (2013). Possible effects of dietary polyphenols on sugar absorption and
695 digestion. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 57, 48–57.
- 696 Xiao, J. (2015). Dietary flavonoid aglycones and their glycosides: which show better
697 biological significance? *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* (in press)
- 698 Xing, S., Wang, M., Peng, Y., Chen, D., & Li, X. (2014). Simulated gastrointestinal
699 tract metabolism and pharmacological activities of water extract of *Scutellaria*
700 *baicalensis* roots. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 152, 183–189.
- 701 Yang, H., Protiva, P., Cui, B., Ma, C., Baggett, S., Hequet, V., Mori, S., Westein, B., &
702 Kennelly, E. J. (2003). New bioactive polyphenols from *Theobroma grandiflorum*
703 (“cupuaçu”). *Journal of Natural Products*, 66, 1501–1504.
- 704 Zanotti, I., Dall’Asta, M., Mena, P., Mele, L., Bruni, R., Ray, S., & Del Rio, D. (2015).
705 Atheroprotective effects of (poly)phenols: a focus on cell cholesterol metabolism.
706 *Food & Function*, 6, 13–31.
- 707 Zhang, J., Cai, W., Zhou, Y., Liu, Y., Wu, X., Li, Y., Lu, J., & Qiao, Y. (2015).
708 Profiling and identification of the metabolites of baicalin and study on their tissue
709 distribution in rats by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography with linear
710 ion trap-Orbitrap mass spectrometer. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 985, 91–102.
- 711

Table 1. HPLC-DAD-IT analysis and content (mg/g d.w.) of flavone glucuronides and clovamide in cupuassu phenolic extract (CPE).

No	Compound	tr (min)	[M-H] ⁻	MS/MS fragments	Content (mg/g d.w.)
1	Clovamide	20.01	358	222, 178, 161	23.03 ± 0.25
2	Hypolaetin 8-O-β-D glucuronide	25.93	477	301	22.13 ± 0.07
3	Isoscutellarein 8-O-β-D glucuronide	28.25	461	285	10.63 ± 0.03
4	Hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O-β-D glucuronide	28.47	491	315, 301	7.81 ± 0.02
5	Hypolaetin 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulfate	36.21	557	447, 301, 255	9.07 ± 0.03
6	Isoscutellarein 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulfate	43.59	541	461, 285, 255	23.06 ± 0.04
7	Hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulfate	44.30	571	491, 315, 255	14.76 ± 0.25

Table 2. Quantification of procyanidins in cupuassu phenolic extract (CPE) by phloroglucinolysis.

Compound	tr (min)	[M-H]⁻	mg/g d.w.
Epicatechin adduct (extension unit)	8.23	413	31.23
Epicatechin (terminal unit)	14.99	289	29.17
Total Epicatechin			60.40
Catechin (terminal unit)	11.12	289	2.20
Total flavan-3-ols			62.61
mDP*			2.00

*mDP= mean degree of polymerization

Table 3. Parent compounds (A) and main metabolites (B) identified along the gastrointestinal tract after the intake of cupuassu phenolic extract.

No	Compounds	Retention time (min)	Exact mass	MS/MS fragments	Score	Error	Molecular Formula	Samples ^{a)}
A) PARENT COMPOUNDS								
P1	Procyanidin B2	4.95	577.1351	289, 245, 125	92.21	0.27	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	ST, SI, CE, C*
P2	Epicatechin	5.42	289.0718	245, 203, 137, 125, 109	99.91	0.19	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	ST, SI, CE, C
P3	Clovamide	6.08	358.0932	178, 161, 135	99.21	0.75	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₇	ST, SI, CE, C
P4	Hypolaetin 8-O-β-D glucuronide	9.05	477.0675	301, 175	94.70	0.40	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₃	ST, SI,
P5	Hypolaetin 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulphate	10.48	557.0243	477, 301, 255	90.84	0.53	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₆ S	ST, SI, CE, C, F
P6	Hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O-β-D glucuronide	10.74	491.0831	315, 300, 175	94.24	1.91	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₁₃	ST, SI,
P7	Isoscutellarein 8-O-β-D glucuronide	10.85	461.0725	285, 175	92.48	2.52	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	ST, SI,
P8	Hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulphate	12.24	571.0399	491, 315, 255	97.87	1.32	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₁₆ S	ST, SI, CE, C, F
P9	Isoscutellarein 8-O-β-D glucuronide 3''-sulphate	12.52	541.0294	461, 285, 255	98.34	-0.34	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₅ S	ST, SI, CE, C, F
B) METABOLITES								
M1	Sulphate derivative of M2	4.42/6.58	397.0592	315, 271, 205, 163, 151, 135, 123, 109	93.55	1.63	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₉ S	SI, CE, C, F
M2	Unknown	5.23/5.76	317.1031	193, 151, 135, 123, 109	92.45	0.21	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₆	CE, C, F
M3	3,4-diHPP-2-ol	5.63	291.0874	247, 205, 167, 151, 135, 123, 109	96.77	2.50	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₆	CE, C, F
M4	5-(3-Hydroxyphenyl)-γ-valerolactone sulphate	5.81	271.0282	191	96.44	0.73	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₆ S	SI, CE, C, F
M5	5-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-γ-valerolactone	6.20	207.0663	175, 163, 143, 122	96.13	1.46	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄	CE, C,
M6	Unknown*	6.47/7.53	333.0980	-	99.26	0.81	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₇	CE C F
M7	3,4-dihydroxyphenylvaleric acid*	7.22	209.0819	-	92.57	0.18	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄	CE C F
M8	3-HPP-2-ol	7.56	275.0925	191, 167, 147, 125, 107	98.22	2.05	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₅	CE, C, F
M9	Hypolaetin	9.49	301.0354	133, 104, 89, 65	98.40	1.83	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	ST, SI*, CE, C, F
M10	Isoscutellarein	11.50	285.0405	117, 65	97.75	2.00	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	ST, SI*, CE, C, F
M11	Hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether	12.23	315.0510	133, 65	90.81	2.10	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	ST, CE, C, F

a) Sample identification, ST: stomach; SI: small intestine; CE: caecum; C: colon; F: feces . *Detected at traces level. M6 and M7 were detected at too low intensity to obtain optima MS/MS analysis.

Figure 1. Structures of the main compounds found in cupuassu phenolic extract (CPE) and the main microbial metabolites identified in tissue samples. Numbers correspond to compounds described in Table 1.

Figure 2. HPLC-UV chromatogram at 340 nm of cupuassu phenolic extract (CPE). Number correspond to compounds described in Table 1. (1) clovamide; (2) hypolaetin 8-O- β -D-glucuronide; (3) isoscutellarein 8-O- β -D-glucuronide; (4) hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O- β -D-glucuronide; (5) hypolaetin 8-O- β -D-glucuronide 3''-O-sulfate; (6) isoscutellarein 8-O- β -D-glucuronide 3''-O-sulfate; (7) hypolaetin 3'-methyl ether 8-O- β -D-glucuronide 3''-O-sulfate.

Figure 3. Extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of the parent compounds (P) and main microbial metabolites (M) identified in (A) stomach (0.5 h after cupuassu administration) and (B) colon (4 h after cupuassu administration). Numbers correspond to compounds identified in Table 3. Two isomers of M1 and M2 were observed while no peaks were included for M6 and M7 because of the low intensity of the peaks (in traces).

Figure 4. Distribution of parent compounds from Cupuassu phenolic extract : A) clovamide, B) epicatechin, C) procyanidin B2, D) hypolaetin glucuronide F) hypolaetin glucuronide-sulphate and the main flavone metabolite F) hypolaetin in different tissues along the gastrointestinal tract: stomach (●), small intestine (■), cecum (▲) colon (◇). Values are means of three mice with SD shown by vertical bars. Results are expressed in Areas corrected by the ratio mg of tissue/mL of extraction solvent.

